

Comparative Analysis between Marital Counselling and Family Planning among Married Women in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State

Ajagbe, Seun Weyinmi¹

Yekinni, Lukuman Oyewole¹

yekingwolex09@gmail.com
+2348032262650

Babatunde, Stephen Ishola²

batatundekayode123@gmail.com
+2348038579822

Kareem, Kazeem Kayode¹

k.k.k.@gmail.com
+2348032308532

¹ Department of Educational Psychology, School of Education, Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Oyo State, Nigeria

² Department of Psychology, Atiba University, Oyo. Oyo State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study analysis comparatively, the relationships between marital counselling and family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, hence, a survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research hypotheses were formulated and the results of the study showed that there was positive relationship between acceptance of family planning $r = .155$, $P < .005$ and family planning $t(8) = 1.502$, < 0.05). Family planning methods would include every measure that can be taken so as to give a couple their required freedom to determine when they want to have their children and what the time gap should be if planning more than one child. It was concluded that marriage counselling is appropriate for all married women as this allows for appropriate family planning. It was recommended that family counselling should be made compulsory for intending couple in Nigeria as this will help reduce the incidence of unplanned pregnancy and premature death among children.

Keyword: Counselling, Family planning, Marriage, Married women

Introduction

The institution of marriage allows a man and a woman to join a family. It is a committed partnership when a man and a woman are accepted as parents by society. Hindu marriage is considered the sacred fulfilment of religious obligations (Naylor, 2014). Marriage is viewed less as a relationship between two young people and more as a union between two joint families. According to the psychological framework, getting married opens the door to having a close, personal relationship with someone who is the other sex. The marital life quality of couples is determined by their interactions and marital relationship. To lessen marital discord, marriage counselling offers a wide range of technical solutions (Siji & Rekha, 2018). Marriage counselling typically focuses on solving the current issues that are presenting, offers emotional support to the spouses, and increases their optimism and sense of self-worth. One form of psychotherapy that married couples or long-term partners can use to address issues in their relationship is marriage counselling. Usually, two persons meet for therapy to talk about particular concerns (Siji & Rekha, 2018).

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Based on psychotherapy and family systems, marriage counselling aims to comprehend the symptoms of its clients and how their interactions lead to marital issues. Problems in the relationship can usually be resolved in a few sessions of short-term therapy (Haruna & Gurjiya, 2022). Counsellors for marriages typically inquire about the roles, norms, objectives, and beliefs of the couple (Siji & Rekha, 2018). Therapy frequently starts with the couple discussing the positive and negative elements of their relationship. Following that, the marriage counsellor works with the couple to assist them see that, most of the time, both parties are responsible for relationship issues. Once this is realised, the two can work together to modify their interactions in order to resolve issues. It could be suggested that the partners draft a contract in which each one outlines the conduct they plan to uphold. It is not necessary for two people to be married in order for them to seek marriage counselling. Help with behavioural challenges, relationship problems, or mental or emotional disorders is available to anyone looking to enhance their relationship. Premarital therapy is a service provided by marriage counsellors to help couples identify possible trouble areas before they get married. In this study, "marriage counselling" refers exclusively to counselling after marriage.

Young adults have exceptional physical functioning, vitality, and health. Young adults have not yet experienced the physical degeneration that comes with ageing, such as wrinkles, weakening body systems, and diminished heart and lung function. They are at their peak in terms of strength, coordination, reaction time, senses (taste, smell, touch, hearing, etc.), fine motor skills, and sexual response. Furthermore, young men and women alike reap the rewards of society's emphasis on youth. Generally speaking, they have an alluring appearance, sensual appeal, and allure. All or most of the hair, well-defined muscles, and good skin can be found in young men. A tiny waist, toned legs, thighs, and buttocks, and soft, supple skin are common characteristics of young women. The idea that older women are passé while older men are respected has been the fundamental cause of the double standard of ageing that neither gender has really experienced until recently. With their youthful beauty, excellent health, and boundless vitality, young adults fantasise and plan. Many adults in their 20s and 30s have a long list of goals they hope to achieve, ranging from becoming a billionaire before the age of 30 to completing graduate school and starting a family. Nothing appears difficult when you're a young adult; everything is achievable if you have the correct mindset, enough perseverance, and energy. Early in life, a person's main concerns are learning how to share intimacy, forming connections, and discovering intimate love (Camba, 2015).

Marital Satisfaction: The Impact of Premarital and Couples Counselling was the subject of a 2017 study by Mrozek & Mitchell. This study looked at the relationship between premarital and marital counselling and couples' marital satisfaction. The results revealed a pattern indicating that those who participated in premarital counselling reported higher levels of marital satisfaction than those who did not. In a research on the impact of a psycho-communicative-educational intervention on marriage, Teal (2018) evaluated the couples who were transitioning to motherhood one year after the intervention. In comparison to a control group, the results indicated that the psycho-communicative-educational preventive intervention was generally more successful for wife and husband marital quality, postpartum depression, and for the husband and wife's antagonistic behaviour as seen on the marriage dispute videotapes.

Mature psychological equilibrium and maturity are necessary for marriage, a lifelong institution, to handle the myriad obstacles that may arise (Adzovie Dabone, 2021). There are various procedures that must be followed when a man and a woman decide to start a family; these procedures vary depending on the tribe and culture. Pre-marital counselling, on the other hand, is thought to be one of the greatest practices since it helps prospective couples better comprehend the school they are going to be admitted to. In the past,

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premarital counselling gained popularity in the 20th century and has continued to grow in popularity among elites. According to Naylor (2014), premarital counselling refers to the services that licenced professionals provide to those who are considering or have expressed a desire to enter into a marriage. This means that premarital counselling has a significant role in influencing marriage success.

An estimated 536,000 women and girls worldwide pass away from pregnancy-related causes each year; that is one death per minute (World Health Organisation, 2013). If nothing had been done, there's a chance the number would have skyrocketed. More than 99 percent of maternal deaths happen in underdeveloped nations, with Sub-Saharan Africa accounting for over half of these deaths. Sub-Saharan African women actually have a higher chance of dying during childbirth than women in any other part of the world. This is particularly true for African women between the ages of 15 and 19, for whom giving birth is the primary cause of death. Moreover, up to 20 million girls and women are thought to die each year in the world. Endure chronic illness while managing to survive childbirth, a condition known as maternal morbidities. Maternal deaths during pregnancy, childbirth, or the postpartum period are caused by a variety of reasons. The majority of these issues arise from the pregnancy itself, and some happen when an underlying illness has gotten worse during pregnancy. Infections (also primarily soon after birth), hypertensive disorders in pregnancy (eclampsia), severe bleeding (mostly postpartum), and obstructed labour are the four main deaths (United Nations Children's Fund (2007)).¹⁵ Maternal deaths from complications following an unsafe abortion account for 13% of cases. Approximately 80% of maternal fatalities worldwide are caused by these direct factors. Thus, it can be argued categorically that illnesses like malaria, anaemia, and HIV that worsen or complicate pregnancy are among the indirect causes of maternal death (20%). Inadequate prenatal care and poor health at conception are some reasons why women die during pregnancy rather than having a healthy pregnancy and healthy offspring.

The majority of women in Nigeria do not have complete access to maternal healthcare, despite several developed and developing nations having made progress in this area. This is because, among other reasons, there is insufficient information about health care availability, personnel shortages, or lack of availability. Because most traditional forms of delivery have long been valued in Southwest Nigeria, most women, particularly those living in rural areas, are reluctant to use health care facilities, despite the significant risks associated with doing so. Inadequate data hinders government organisations in charge of providing significant health care from carrying out projects in the most efficient manner, and barriers to access and affordability keep women from taking advantage of the resources that are available. It is undeniable that in recent years, women's access to prenatal, postpartum, and post-delivery health care has improved, despite the fact that cost was a contributing factor in this lack of access in the past. This was created to guarantee that women's and children's mortality rates are as low as possible.

It is possible to view family planning as a way to prevent maternal illnesses and mortality. When a couple plans their family, they talk about when and how many kids they can have in order to provide the best possible care for the child—financially, mentally, and socially. Although birth control and contraception are frequently associated with family planning, family planning is potentially much more than that. Every step that may be done to grant a couple the necessary flexibility to choose when they want to have children and how long to wait between them, if they are planning more than one, is included in family planning strategies. Deciding how many children to have and when to have them is the goal of family planning. This probably has to do with when pregnancies occur and how far apart babies are born. The World Health Organisation (2013) states that in order to lower the dangers to the mother and child, a minimum of 24 months should elapse before attempting another pregnancy. If a woman engages in sexual

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activity after giving birth and does not nurse exclusively, she may become pregnant a few weeks later. For this reason, it is important to talk about this with a counsellor or healthcare professional who can provide expert direction towards appropriate spacing and a happy family.

Statement of the Research Problem

In Akure South Local Government, there are not enough comprehensive marital counselling programmes designed to meet the unique requirements and difficulties married women encounter. This divide could impede couples' ability to resolve conflicts, communicate effectively, and enjoy a happy marriage. Access to reliable information and high-quality family planning services may be impeded for married women residing in the area. Low use of family planning techniques may be caused by a number of factors, including cultural attitudes, ignorance, and a lack of access to quality healthcare. Misconceptions about contraceptive methods and the social stigma associated with family planning may prevent married women from making educated decisions regarding their reproductive health. It is essential to address these myths by implementing focused education and awareness initiatives. The impact of married women's decisions about family planning in Akure on approval from their spouses The South Local Government presents a major obstacle. A spouse's lack of support or participation in family planning conversations may restrict a woman's ability to make decisions about her reproductive health. Investigating the region's teenage population's knowledge and use of contraception is necessary. Adolescent reproductive health outcomes may be impacted by elements like parental supervision, educational initiatives, and availability to contraceptive services. Through focused interventions, policy modifications, and community involvement, stakeholders can improve married women's reproductive health outcomes and general well-being in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The study aims to compare and analyse the relationship between marital counseling and family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study worked on the following objectives:

1. Investigate the relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria;
2. Examine the implications of marital counselling and the method of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria and
3. Investigate family planning among women exposed to marital counselling and those not exposed in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study therefore raised three (3) research questions for the purpose of achieving this work

1. What is the relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among married women in Ondo State?
 2. What are the families planning methods mostly adopted by married women in Ondo State?
- What are the discrepancies between women exposed to family planning and those that are not exposed to in Ondo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance

- HO1: There is no significant relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria
- HO2: There will be no significant relationship between marital counselling and the method of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria
- HO3: Investigate family planning among women exposed to marital counselling and those not exposed in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design of the correlational type. This method was used to gather the opinions of respondents on the influence of marital counselling on the acceptance of family planning by married women. The population used for this study comprised all married women in the Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample size for this study was one hundred (100) married women, drawn randomly from the public. A simple random sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. The age range of the samples used for the study was between twenty

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and sixty years of age. The adapted version of the Couple Therapy Questionnaire was used in the study. This instrument was developed by Shull (2000). The original version of the instrument was used to elicit information from clients who are still in the process of getting married. The instrument has a 0.087 alpha beta coefficient and, as such, was considered reliable for the purpose of the study. Hence, the adapted version was used to elicit information from married individuals. The researcher met each of the participants. The purpose of the research was adequately explained to the participants, and each participant was assured of the utmost confidentiality of the information supplied. Therefore, the questionnaires were administered to the participants, and at the end of the exercise, the questionnaires were retrieved for data analysis. The collected data were analysed using Pearson product-movement correlation and multiple regression analysis.

Results

Research Hypothesis 1; there is no significant relationship between marital counselling and acceptance of family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The table reveals that there is a significant positive relationship between acceptability of family planning and marital counselling among women. Marital counselling correlates ($r = 0.155, p < .001$), and family planning ($r = 0.155, p < .001$). This implies that the level of family planning acceptability can be traced to the level of marital counselling provided by counsellors.

Table 1: shows Zero Order Correlation Showing the Relationship between marital counselling and acceptability of family planning among women

Variable	N	Mean	St-Dev	Df	r	P
Acceptability of family planning	100	54.9103	8.01718	183		
Marital counselling	100	1.4421	0.49751	194	0.155	<.001

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Sig. at 0.05 level

Research Hypothesis 2; there is no significant relationship between marital counselling and the method of family planning among women in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria Table heading. The table 2 shows that $t_{(8)} = -1.502, P > 0.05$. This indicates that there is significant relationship in the marital counselling provided by counsellors and the choice of married men towards different method of family planning. In essence, this result shows that the different methods used by married women in family were due to the counselling services received from competent counsellors.

Table 2: Relationship between marital counselling and method of family planning among women

Relationship	N	x	SD	df	T	Sig.	Remark
Methods of family planning	89	45.00	8.00	858.5	1.502	1.001	Sig.
Marital Counselling	11	52.67	13.715				
Total	100						

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

Research Hypothesis 3: states that family planning among women exposed to marital counselling and those not exposed in Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The table above shows that there is a significant difference in the influence of married women who received counselling on family planning and those who did not receive any counselling ($F_{(3,249)} = 35.213, P < 0.05$) which is statistically significant.

Table 3 shows the difference between exposed and not exposed women to family planning

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Level of acceptance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Counseled	121.000	123	211.120	35.213	.000*
Not counseled	023.589	3	.621		

Source: Author’s Survey, 2024

Discussion of Findings

The result from research hypothesis 1 indicated that prior counselling on family planning provided married women with the option to accept and make use of the available methods for planning their families. This implies that the level of family planning acceptability can be traced to the level of marital counseling provided by counselors. This study correlates with the findings of Larson & Olson (2019), who found that the competence and effectiveness of controlling birthrate are due to proper orientation about different types and mediums of family planning among women. There is no doubt, therefore, that providing counselling services in relation to family planning could boost the acceptability of different methods by women. Counselling is considered necessary when it comes to family setup. Invariably, planning the family in relation to childbirth is synonymous with the level of counselling services provided.

The result of research hypothesis 2 revealed that there is a significant relationship between marital counselling and the method of family planning among women. Invariably, the method that individual women prefer could be attributed to the level of counselling provided by competent counsellors. There is no doubt that this finding negates the work of Johansson (2016), who found out that, especially in many parts of Africa, women must seek permission from their husband or family to visit a clinic for care. Even when permission is nominally given, women’s lack of autonomy in their families can still prevent them from seeking care and birth control. However, the present study corroborates the findings by Fowers and Olson (2016) that family members may consider childbirth as a woman’s concern and not that of the household. As a result, women may find it difficult to get the money to pay for services or to obtain transportation to get medical care.

The result of research hypothesis 3 states that the importance of counselling cannot be underemphasized in this study. It was established in this study that counselling is an integral part of day-to-day activities and, as such, cannot be considered less. This was obvious in the outcome of the study, as it was found that women who understand marital counselling should have a higher level of acceptance of family planning than those who are not ounseled. There is a need to stress the fact that marital counselling gives married women the opportunity to adequately plan their family as regards birth control when counselling services are put in motion. This work is in line with the work of Cuervo-Arango et al. (2019), which reported a retrospective comparison of the efficiency of different assisted reproductive techniques in horses, emphasising the impact of maternal age.

Conclusion

The study examines the role of marital counseling and family planning among married women in Akure South Local Government. It highlights the importance of both services in addressing conflicts, improving communication, and fostering healthy relationships. Family planning is crucial for reproductive health and well-being, enabling informed decisions about pregnancy timing and spacing. However, utilization patterns vary due to cultural norms, religious beliefs, socioeconomic status, and awareness levels. The study suggests that policymakers need to consider comprehensive strategies to address these challenges, such as expanding counseling services, increasing awareness about family planning options, and addressing socio-cultural barriers. Further research is needed to explore the long-term effects of these interventions on marital stability, reproductive health outcomes, and family dynamics.

Recommendations

From the foregoing, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Encourage the integration of marital counseling and family planning services within existing healthcare facilities should be made compulsory. This approach ensures that married women have access to comprehensive reproductive health services that address both relational and contraceptive needs.

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- ii. Launch targeted awareness campaigns should be organized to educate married women and their families about the benefits of marital counseling and family planning. Engage community leaders, religious institutions, and local organizations to disseminate accurate information and dispel myths or misconceptions.
- iii. Tailor counseling and family planning programs to align with the cultural and religious beliefs prevalent should be embedded in Akure South Local Government for married women. Provide culturally sensitive counseling services and incorporate religious perspectives into family planning education to increase acceptability and uptake.

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